

ALKYLATION OF KETONES. PART II

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Higher alkyl groups have been introduced in a ketone by the action of sodamide and the corresponding alkyl halide. *n*-Amyl derivatives of cyclohexanone, cyclopentanone and 3-methylcyclopentanone have been synthesised.

In a previous paper on the subject (this *Journal*, 1949, 26, 483) it has been shown that a convenient method for alkylation of a ketone consists in preparing 2-formyl ketone which with sodium ethylate and alkyl halide forms 2-formyl-2-alkyl ketone. On removing the formyl group from the latter by ketonic hydrolysis, 2-alkyl ketone results.

In attempting to introduce higher alkyl groups by this method, however, we found that the reactions proceeded differently. For instance, with 2-formylcyclohexanone and *n*-amyl bromide in presence of sodium ethylate, the main product of reaction was a neutral liquid having a composition corresponding to that of 2-formyl-2-*n*-amylcyclohexanone (I). The latter on hydrolysis with aqueous potash did not, however, yield the expected 2-*n*-amylcyclohexanone, but a liquid mixture of cyclohexanone and *n*-amyl alcohol. The former was identified from the melting points of its semicarbazone and of 2 : 4-dinitrophenylhydrazone which the mixture yielded, and the latter from its boiling point, smell and formation of its characteristic green crystalline complex with anhydrous cupric chloride (Lloyd *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 666). Although no other solid derivative of *n*-amyl alcohol could be obtained from the mixture, an independently prepared mixture of cyclohexanone and *n*-amyl alcohol in almost equal proportion behaved exactly in boiling range and chemical properties like this product of hydrolysis. The alkylation did not therefore produce the expected *C*-amyl derivative (I) but probably the *O*-amyl ether of hydroxymethylenecyclohexanone (II), an isomer of (I).

O-Alkylation of a formyl ketone has been recorded by Bishop, Claisen and Sinclair (*Annalen*, 1894, 281, 367) who obtained *O*-methyl ether of hydroxymethylene camphor from methyl iodide, sodium ethylate and hydroxymethylene camphor. The ether was hydrolysed by alcoholic potash to hydroxymethylene camphor (*loc. cit.*). In the case of ether (II), the hydrolysis seems to have gone a step further with loss of formyl group, the ultimate products being cyclohexanone and *n*-amyl alcohol.

The method of introducing small alkyl groups in ketones through the intermediate formyl derivatives, which we have described in the previous paper, did not thus succeed with larger alkyl, like *n*-amyl group, in the case of cyclohexanone. Attempts to prepare *n*-amyl derivatives of cyclopentanone and 3-methylcyclopentanone by the same method, were similarly unsuccessful.

Although with a ketone and sodium, the main reactions are reduction and condensation (Agarwal and Deshapande, *loc. cit.*), the use of sodamide in place of sodium precludes reduction, allowing thereby the formation of sodium compound of the ketone to take place. Alkylation can then be effected through the sodium compound. Thus, with sodamide and methyl iodide, Haller (*Compt. rend.*, 1913, 156, 1199) obtained polymethylcyclohexanones from cyclohexanone. We have now successfully used this method and obtained *n*-amyl derivatives of cyclohexanone (III), cyclopentanone (IV), and 3-methylcyclopentanone (V) or (VI) from the respective ketones.

The alkylation products are true ketones as they give well characterised semicarbazones.

The amyl derivative of the unsymmetrical 3-methylcyclopentanone formed by this process may be either 5-amyl (V) or 2-amyl (VI) derivative. If it is (VI), it should be identical with the product of reduction of jasmone—the odoriferous component of jasmine perfume—to which the structure (VII) is assigned (Ruzicka and Pfeiffer, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1933, 16, 1208). Tetrahydrojasmone (b.p. 101°/12 mm.) has been synthesised by Treff and Werner (*Ber.*, 1933, 60B, 1521) and its structure (VI) is confirmed. The melting point of the semicarbazone of the synthetic ketone has been recorded by them as 165°. The *l*-form of this ketone is obtained by the catalytic reduction of tetrahydropyretrolone (which was itself prepared by reduction of pyretrolone of insect powder by Staudinger and Ruzicka, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1924, 7, 236). The *l*-ketone forms a semicarbazone melting at 194°. The ketone that we have prepared by direct amylation of optically inactive 3-methylcyclopentanone boils at 145°-148°/12 mm., while the racemic form of (VI) boils at 101°/12 mm. Further, the semicarbazone of our optically inactive ketone melts at 190°; and that of the racemic form of (VI) melts at 165°. Our ketone cannot therefore be (VI) and, therefore by inference, it is probably (V). (For a similar case cf. Ruhemann and Levy, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, 101, 2552).

EXPERIMENTAL

O-Amyl Ether of Hydroxymethylenecyclohexanone.—To 2-formylcyclohexanone (b.p. 110°/12 mm., 12.6 g.) was added an alcoholic solution of sodium ethylate, prepared from sodium (2.3 g.)

and absolute alcohol (70 g.). A gelatinous orange colored sodium compound separated. To this, well cooled in ice, was added *n*-amyl bromide (b.p. 129°, 15.1g.), the mixture was allowed to remain at room temperature for two days with occasional shaking, and finally refluxed on a water-bath for 4 hours when it became neutral. After evaporating the alcohol, the product was poured into water, made slightly acid and the oily layer separating was extracted with ether. After washing, drying and removing the solvent, the residual liquid was fractionated when the main fraction (8 g., b.p. 90°—100°/120 mm.) was obtained as a colorless, mobile, neutral liquid with a characteristic smell. As the product was to be used as an intermediate for the next experiment of hydrolysis, it was not further purified. (Found: C, 71.6; H, 10.3. $C_{11}H_{20}O_2$ requires C, 73.4; H, 10.2 per cent). It forms a semicarbazone, m.p. 162°.

Hydrolysis.—The product (7g.) was hydrolysed by refluxing with 10% aqueous potash for 8 hours. On extracting the oily layer with ether, washing, drying and removing the solvent, a liquid was left which was fractionated at atmospheric pressure, when the main fraction (4.5 g.) was collected between 140° and 144° and about 1g. passed above 146°. From its low boiling point it could be seen that the main fraction cannot contain *n*-amylcyclohexanone. It yielded a semicarbazone, m.p. 166° and a 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone, m.p. 160° (cyclohexanone, b.p. 155°; semicarbazone, m.p. 166°; 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone, m.p. 160°). Anhydrous cupric chloride left in contact with the fraction gave a green crystalline copper salt comparable with that prepared from *n*-amyl alcohol (b.p. 138°).

2-Formylcyclopentanone and 3-methyl-2-formyl (or 5-formyl) cyclopentanone, which could not be used successfully for the purpose of higher alkylation, have been described by Wallach and Steindorff (*Annalen*, 1903, 329, 114, 116). These compounds have again been prepared and characterised as follows.

2-Formylcyclopentanone: Pale yellow needles, m.p. 76° (W. & S., m.p. 73°) (Found: C, 64.0; H, 7.6. $C_6H_8O_2$ requires C, 64.3; H, 7.1 per cent). Semicarbazone, m.p. 185°. Its green chelate copper compound crystallises from chloroform-petroleum ether mixture and melts at 172°. (Found: Cu, 21.8. $C_{12}H_{14}O_4Cu$ requires Cu, 22.2 per cent).

3-Methyl-2-formyl (or 5-formyl) cyclopentanone: Pale yellow needles, m.p. 58° (W. & S., m.p. 54°; Ruhemann & Levy, *loc. cit.*, m.p. 58°). (Found: C, 66.4; H, 8.2. $C_7H_{10}O_2$ requires C, 66.6; H, 7.9 per cent). Semicarbazone, m.p. 194°. Green chelate copper salt, m.p. 183°. (Found: Cu, 19.8. $C_{14}H_{18}O_4Cu$ requires Cu, 20.2 per cent).

2-n-Amylcyclohexanone.—Sodamide (6.0 g., coarse granules, B.D.H.) was added in instalments to cyclohexanone (16.5 g.) diluted with dry ether-benzene mixture. The mixture was heated on a water-bath under dry conditions till ammonia ceased to be evolved (6 hours). *n*-Amyl bromide (23 g.) was then added and heating continued until the mixture showed slight alkalinity (8 hours). A further instalment of *n*-amyl bromide (5 g.) was added and heating continued for another 3 hours, when the reaction was neutral. The product was poured into water, the ether-benzene layer which separated was washed and dried, and after removal of the solvent, the residual liquid was distilled at atmospheric pressure till the temperature rose to 160°, when the unchanged cyclohexanone and *n*-amyl bromide distilled off. The residue was then fractionated under reduced pressure. The main fraction (5.5 g.) was collected at 128°-130°/12 mm. It is a colorless, neutral liquid with fragrant smell. (Found: C, 78.2; H, 11.4. $C_{11}H_{20}O$ requires C, 78.57; H, 11.9 per cent). Cyclohexanone requires C, 73.5; H, 10.2 per cent). The semicarbazone crystallises from dilute alcohol and melts at 178°.

2-n-Amylcyclopentanone was prepared as in the above manner. *cyclopentanone* (16.8 g.), sodamide (7.8 g.) and *n*-amyl bromide (30 g.) yielded *2-n-amlylcyclopentanone* (7.8 g.) as a colorless, mobile liquid, b.p. 138° - $140^{\circ}/12$ mm. (Found: C, 77.9; H, 11.0. $C_{10}H_{18}O$ requires C, 77.9; H, 11.69 per cent). Its semicarbazone melts at 175° . (Found: N, 19.6. $C_{11}H_{21}ON_3$ requires N, 19.9 per cent).

3-Methyl-5-n-amlylcyclopentanone was similarly prepared as in the above manner. *3-Methylcyclopentanone* (10 g., b.p. 143°), sodamide (4g.) and *n*-amyl bromide (15.2 g.) yielded the product (5 g.) as a colorless liquid (b.p. 146° - $148^{\circ}/12$ mm.) with almost no odour. (Found: C, 78.2; H, 11.1. $C_{11}H_{20}O$ requires C, 78.57; H, 11.9 per cent). Its semicarbazone melts at 190° with decomposition. (Found: N, 19.1. $C_{12}H_{23}ON_3$ requires N, 18.7 per cent).

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